

4-Nitrophenylazoacetic Acid and its Derivatives

P. S. FERNANDES, V. V. NADKARNY, (Miss) G. A. JABBAR
and (Miss) R. P. JANI

Nadkarny-Sacasa Research Laboratory, St. Xavier's College, Bombay-1.

Manuscript received 29 March 1975, revised 25 June 1975, accepted 2 July 1975

4-Nitrophenylazoacetic acid was obtained by coupling malonic ester with diazotised *p*-nitraniline and subsequent hydrolysis and decarboxylation. This was then converted to its acid chloride and condensed with a few amines and phenols. 4-Nitrophenylazoacetic acid hydrazide and *N*-benzylidene-4-nitrophenylazoacetic acid hydrazides were also prepared.

THE β -keto esters are known to give hydrazones¹ when coupled with diazonium salts. Similarly malonic ester was shown to give hydrazones² when coupled with diazonium salts. The hydrazone of malonic ester exists in two isomeric forms.

Hence the acid obtained by the hydrolysis of the above ester could also exist in two isomeric forms.

The hydrazones of the type (A) can be obtained by condensing phenylhydrazines with glyoxylic acid³. Similar hydrazones were also obtained by the reaction between chloral hydrate and phenylhydrazines⁴.

In this investigation the diazonium salt of *p*-nitraniline was coupled with malonic ester in acetone solution containing sodium acetate. The orange

SCHEME A

SCHEME B

coloured dye that separated out was hydrolysed by boiling with strong alkali and subsequently decarboxylated by boiling with a strong mineral acid. The compound thus obtained may probably have the structure I (scheme A) rather than the hydrazone. The compound I was found to be extremely stable towards concentrated hydrochloric acid even on prolonged boiling. If the compound existed in the form of its hydrazone, it would have undergone hydrolysis, since phenylhydrazones are susceptible to acid hydrolysis.

The compound I even on prolonged boiling with acid did not give glyoxylic acid and 4-nitrophenylhydrazine hydrochloride; instead the original compound was isolated without any loss. This proved conclusively that the compound I (scheme A) exists as the azo compound and not as its hydrazone. The I.R. spectra also gave characteristic absorption peaks for all the functional groups viz., 1712 cm^{-1} , 1650 cm^{-1} , 1520 cm^{-1} , 1342 cm^{-1} . Further the NMR data could not be obtained since the compound was insoluble in most solvents used for the NMR spectra.

The 4-nitrophenylazoacetic acid was then converted to its chloride and condensed with few of the amines and phenols (scheme A). The compound I was also converted to the corresponding hydrazide which was subsequently reacted with some aldehydes (scheme B).

Experimental

4-Nitrophenylazoacetic acid (I)

To an ice-cold solution of malonic ester (0.1 mole) in acetone containing sodium acetate was gradually added a diazotised solution of 4-nitraniline (0.1 mole) with stirring and cooling. The reaction mixture was further stirred for an hour at 0°–5°, after which it was allowed to stand at room temperature overnight. The orange coloured azo compound separating out was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from alcohol.

The azo compound obtained as above was hydrolysed by boiling with excess of alkali (3–4 hr). This mixture was cooled and acidified with concentrated hydrochloric acid and boiled for 1½–2 hr to bring about the decarboxylation. The precipitated compound (I) was filtered, washed with water and crystallised from 50% alcohol. M.P. 205°, yield 69%

(Found : C, 45.69; H, 3.24; N, 19.87; $\text{C}_8\text{H}_7\text{N}_3\text{O}_4$ requires, C, 45.94; H, 3.35; N, 20.09%).

4-Nitrophenylazoacetyl chloride (II)

The compound (I) 0.05 mole was mixed intimately with 10 g PCl_5 . The mixture was heated on a water bath for 3–4 hr. The excess of PCl_5 was then decomposed by the addition of cold water. The precipitated chloride was filtered and washed with cold water. The acid chloride (II) was then purified by dissolving it in benzene and reprecipitating with excess of petroleum ether (40°–60°). M.P. 124°–26°. Yield 59% (Found : N, 19.19; Cl, 16.37; $\text{C}_8\text{H}_6\text{N}_3\text{ClO}_3$ requires, N, 19.31; Cl, 16.32%).

Aryl 4-nitrophenylazoacetamides (II.a)

0.01 mol compound (II) and 0.01 mol of respective amines were heated under reflux for 1 hr. using 20 ml pyridine as a base. It was then cooled and poured into 100 ml cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated compound was filtered, washed with water till free of acid and crystallised from acetone. The derivatives obtained with different amines are listed in Table 1.

Aryl 4-nitrophenylazoacetic esters (II.b)

Compound II (0.01 mol) was dissolved in 20 ml pyridine to which (0.01 mol) of the different phenols were added. During the addition the temperature was maintained from 20°–25°. When the addition was complete the mixture was allowed to stand at that temperature for 20 min and then heated under reflux in a water bath for ½ hr. After cooling, the mixture was poured into 100 ml cold dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated compound was filtered, washed with cold water followed by cold dilute sodium hydroxide (1%). The precipitate was then washed well with cold water till free from base and recrystallised from acetone. This method was adopted, for different phenols to obtain the corresponding derivatives, which are listed in Table 2.

4-Nitrophenylazoacetic acid hydrazide (IV)

An intimate mixture of compound (I) 20 g, thionylchloride (20 ml) and absolute methanol (250 ml) was refluxed for 20 hr. The excess of methanol was distilled off. The contents of the flask were cooled and poured into 300 ml cold water and neutralised

TABLE 1—ARYL-4-NITROPHENYLAZOACETAMIDE (II a)

Sr. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis %	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	C_6H_5	291	72	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{12}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$	19.62	19.49
2.	4- $\text{CH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	272	69	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$	18.79	18.67
3.	4- $\text{NO}_2\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	298	56	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_5\text{O}_5$	21.34	21.20
4.	4- ClC_6H_4	284	70	$\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{11}\text{N}_4\text{ClO}_3$	17.61	17.49
5.	4- $\text{OCH}_3\text{C}_6\text{H}_4$	278	63	$\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_4$	17.83	17.64
6.	1-Naphthyl	187	57	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$	16.77	16.65
7.	2-Naphthyl	281	59	$\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$	16.77	16.59

TABLE 2—ARYL-4-NITROPHENYLAZOACETIC ESTER (II b)

Sr. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis %	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	C ₆ H ₅	226	40	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ N ₃ O ₄	14.73	14.56
2.	4-CH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	215	52	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄	13.95	13.80
3.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	289	44	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₆	16.97	16.78
4.	2-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₃	305	48	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₅	13.33	13.19
5.	1-Naphthol	298	59	C ₁₆ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄	12.54	12.38
6.	2-Naphthol	269	54	C ₁₈ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₄	12.54	12.43

TABLE 3—N-BENZYLIDENE-4-NITROPHENYLAZOACETIC ACID HYDRAZIDE (V)

Sr. No.	Ar	M.P. °C	Yield %	Molecular Formula	Analysis %	
					Calcd.	Found
1.	C ₆ H ₅	257	58	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₃	22.51	22.30
2.	4-NO ₂ C ₆ H ₄	295	67	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ N ₅ O ₅	23.60	23.49
3.	4-OHC ₆ H ₄	251	49	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	21.41	21.27
4.	2-OHC ₆ H ₄	285	52	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₄	21.41	21.33
5.	4-OCH ₃ C ₆ H ₄	210	63	C ₁₆ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₄	20.52	20.45
6.	2-Furyl	269	59	C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₄	23.26	23.19

with sodium carbonate at 5°–10°. The precipitated ester was filtered washed with cold water till the washings were neutral and dried. The crude ester (III) was used for the next stage without further purification (M.P. 145°).

0.1 mole III, 0.2 mole 95% hydrazine hydrate and 50 ml methanol were taken in a 250 ml flask. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 15–17 hr and excess of methanol was distilled off under vacuum. The contents of the flask was cooled and poured into 200 ml cold water. The precipitated compound (IV) was filtered washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol. M.P. 245°, yield 66%. (Found: C, 42.86; H, 3.88; N, 31.3; C₈H₉N₅O₃ requires: C, 43.05; H, 4.03; N, 31.39%).

N-Benzylidene 4-Nitrophenylazoacetic acid hydrazides (V, Table 3):

Equimolecular amounts of hydrazide (IV) and a suitable aldehyde were taken in 50 ml ethanol. The mixture was refluxed for 1–1½ hr. The product separated on cooling, was filtered and recrystallised from acetone.

References

1. V. MEYER, *Ber.*, 1877, 10, 2075.
2. R. MEYER, *Ber.*, 1883, 21, 118.
3. P. P. T. SAH, CHENG-HENG KAO and TA-YU CHANG, *J. Chinese Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 2, 234; *Chem. Abs.*, 1935, 29, 7384.
4. C. TORRES and B. MARTINEZ OLLER, *Anales fis y quim* (Madrid), 1944, 40, 825; *Chem. Abs.* 1949, 42, 1224d.